

D5.2 Report on development of communications activities and materials

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BUILD

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Executive summary

Scope

This report outlines and details the communication and dissemination efforts undertaken as part of the BUILD project, focused on promoting the adoption of public procurement of innovation (PPI) through capacity-building activities. The report summarises the strategies, tools, and materials developed to effectively communicate the project's objectives, engage with stakeholders, and ensure the visibility of its outcomes.

Methodology and structure

The methodology applied in this report consists of the collection, review, and analysis of communication and dissemination efforts, focusing on the following key areas:

- **Overview of communication activities:** defining the core communication and dissemination strategies, as well as expected goals and results.
- **Framework of the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) plan:** outlining the communication and dissemination plan (C&D), engagement strategy, and collaboration with the BUILD consortium, including any adjustments made during the project.
- **Website development:** creation and management of the project website, including its assets, brand identity, and data protection measures.
- **Social media setup:** establishment of social media channels, including LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram, to enhance the project's online presence and engagement.

Communication activities

The BUILD project's communication activities were diverse and covered multiple platforms to reach a wide audience. These efforts included:

- **Participation and organisation of events:** active involvement in internal and external events, including the organisation of the final project event to disseminate results.
- **Production of articles:** creation of relevant articles to promote project outcomes and insights.
- **Social media activity:** regular social media updates, including frequency and the execution of social media campaigns to engage with stakeholders and promote project achievements.
- **Production of newsletters and press releases:** regular newsletters and press releases were created and disseminated to inform stakeholders and the public about the project's progress and milestones.
- **Cross-communication with related initiatives:** collaborative efforts with related EU-funded projects and initiatives to enhance knowledge exchange and expand outreach.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
CA	Consortium Agreement
CSA	Coordination & Support Actions
D	Deliverable
ERS	Exploitation, Replicability & Sustainability
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
M	Month
POI	Procurement of Innovation
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovation
SME	Small & Medium Enterprises
TBD	To Be Determined
WP	Work Package
C&D	Communication and Dissemination

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the report

This report outlines the communication activities and materials developed as part of the BUILD Communication and Support Action (CSA) project. It summarises the implementation of the communication and dissemination plan established in December 2023, during month three of the project.

Effective communication is vital for the success of the BUILD project. It facilitates maximum participation, fosters collaboration, promotes knowledge sharing, gathers input, and expands the PPI community. Furthermore, it enhances access to educational materials, ensuring their long-term sustainability and impact.

To achieve broad visibility for the BUILD project, the communication and dissemination plan was essential for maximising the impact and reach of its activities and results.

The leader of WP5 (PEDAL) oversaw the overall management and support of these activities, developing key tools and materials for all partners throughout the project. All partners actively participated in dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts, demonstrating a strong commitment to effectively sharing the project's results.

This report details the activities undertaken to:

- Leverage existing contacts and networks.
- Conduct publicity and dissemination campaigns for the BUILD project in their respective countries and beyond.
- Enhance engagement on the project's social media accounts and track their performance.
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes.

1.2 Context and core of the BUILD project

The strategic use of procurement to boost demand for innovative goods or services has become an important part of the innovation policy agenda in many European Union (EU) countries. At the same time, it is the core of the new EU public procurement directive. While this underlines importance of opening opportunities for public procurement of innovation (PPI) and significant potential of PPI, there are still several key challenges slowing the widespread adoption

BUILD project (Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities) is primarily focused on enhancing the capability development of public procurers in innovation procurement. The project aims to drive systemic change in how public procurement is leveraged to stimulate innovation, with a specific focus on fostering economic growth through innovative goods and services. BUILD is particularly concerned with upskilling public procurers to accelerate the adoption of innovation across various sectors.

This project spanned for a period of 24 months, from October 2022 until September 2024, and was funded by the European Union's (EU) Horizon Europe programme. During this period, the project operated through a series of work packages, with the consortium delivering various outputs and outcomes as outlined in the project's description of actions. The project team consists of six consortium partners from Slovakia, Estonia, Finland, and the Netherlands.

2 Overview of the communication and dissemination activities

As the leader of WP5, PEDAL oversaw and coordinated the communication and dissemination of various activities, optimising the content produced within the BUILD project. This content was disseminated through multiple platforms—including social media, the website, newsletters, press releases, partner channels, and events—and in various formats such as infographics, factsheets, videos, and images. A range of tools and channels were employed throughout the project to ensure effective messaging to targeted audiences.

Despite the considerable potential of public procurement of innovation (PPI), its widespread adoption remains slow, primarily due to identified challenges. The BUILD project aims to address these challenges while enhancing the capacity of cities in PPI. The activities implemented focus on the following objectives:

1. Encourage cooperation and knowledge sharing

This objective aims to promote the use of public procurement to foster sustainable innovation, creating a fertile platform for future collaboration. BUILD facilitated knowledge exchange among public procurers through various events, fostering mutual learning opportunities. This included simulations of the PPI lifecycle, enabling procurers to demonstrate their learning. Additionally, staff exchanges provided hands-on experiences of different PPI processes through specific case studies.

2. Enhance innovation knowledge and skills

BUILD aims to raise awareness about the co-design process between SMEs and public buyers, helping to identify and develop innovative technological solutions. This was achieved through training and education for public procurers, inspiring them with examples from other cities and countries (WP3). By leveraging multipliers—such as formal clusters and associations, as well as informal groups like community organisations and media—BUILD provided stakeholders with the knowledge and tools necessary for effective PPI implementation (WP1-5).

3. Link with EU research and innovation projects

The BUILD project established synergies with EU-funded projects that promote PPI, particularly in the post-pandemic context. By increasing awareness and knowledge among public and private buyers, the project sought to facilitate the transition from traditional procurement approaches to innovative practices. Dedicated training and the exchange of best practices helped reveal the potential of innovation procurement, ultimately contributing to market growth and addressing societal challenges.

- BUILD supported stakeholders in implementing initiatives that promote the PPI transition by facilitating the exchange of best practices among public procurers at both national and European levels. This includes collaborating with projects like PROCEDIN and InnoFacilitator, establishing the Innovation Procurement Task Force, as well as PPI stakeholders (knowledge centres, policymakers, public buyers, etc.) All public deliverables, milestones, training materials, journal articles, and conference contributions generated by BUILD were transformed into actionable insights, specifically the Educational library, promoting the widespread adoption and replication of the project's outcomes.

4. **Accessible training portfolios**
Providing dedicated training resources enhances skills and capacities for designing innovative procurement strategies.
5. **Awareness of legal frameworks**
Increasing knowledge of the legal frameworks surrounding innovation procurement benefits public buyers and evaluators.
6. **Scale up best practices**
The project aims to elevate successful examples related to need assessment and programme design in innovation procurement.

As a beneficiary of Horizon Europe funding, there is a legal obligation to enhance the impact of project results through:

- **Communication:** creating awareness and engage with the broader public using various channels (social media, newsletters, blogs, press releases, etc.) to inform and educate about the project's scope strategy and outline.
- **Dissemination:** sharing the project results with the public procurement community, industry, civil society, and policymakers, maximizing the impact of the project by ensuring that its outcomes are adopted, used, or further developed by the intended audience.
- **Exploitation:** utilising results to develop, create, or improve products, processes, or services, ultimately benefiting the public.

Importance of these activities

1. **Maximise reach and impact**
Ensuring broad dissemination amplifies the project's influence.
2. **Public good**
Findings, materials, and resources will benefit society, the economy, and the planet.
3. **Support future research**
Facilitating further research and development of new products and services.
4. **Evidence-based policy recommendations**
Contributing to the formulation of informed policy decisions.
5. **Fulfil legal obligations**
Meeting the requirements associated with EU funding.

2.1 Development of the communication and dissemination strategy

2.1.1 Communication and dissemination (C&D) plan

The C&D plan was drafted at the beginning of the project and outlined the following roadmap:

Phase 1: Planning of activities and visual identity (M1 – M3)

- Establish a strong project brand identity.
- Identify the communication and dissemination strategy to maximise the impact of BUILD outcomes.
- Provide consortium partners with promotional materials and templates.

Phase 2: Implementation and monitoring (M3 – M24)

- Implement various communication and dissemination activities.
- Carefully analyse and assess the impact and success of these activities against pre-established key performance indicators (KPIs).

Phase 3: Engagement strategy for innovation procurers (M3 – M14) and implementation of capacity-building activities

- Under WP3, define the value proposition and engagement strategy of the BUILD project. Identify relevant stakeholders for engagement and onboard them based on their level of commitment and interest.
- Establish the basis for training under WP4, implementing the training sessions and staff exchanges and creating actionable knowledge materials.

Phase 4: Sustainability (M3 – M24)

- Identify and establish mechanisms to ensure lasting visibility of BUILD outcomes. During this phase, the exploitation and sustainability plan was developed, considering the results of the C&D activities.

2.1.2 Engagement strategy

Engagement activities are vital to ensure that the project's outcomes reach a broader audience and that the developed materials and resources are effectively utilised and improved over time. To achieve this, the first step was to identify the target groups and key stakeholders. These were outlined during the initial phase of the project and presented in the D5.1 – Communication and Dissemination Plan (December 2023). The key stakeholders identified include:

- public buyers
- SMEs, start-ups, spin-offs
- research and technological institutions
- policymakers
- civil society
- media

This activity was conducted in spring 2023, culminating in April with the creation of D3.1 – Value Proposition and Engagement Strategy. A clearer understanding of stakeholders' tasks, needs, and potential solutions was gained through two key tools: the Empathy Map and the Value Proposition Canvas. Project partners actively participated in these workshops, contributing insights based on their everyday work in public procurement. This exercise helped clarify the appropriate communication and value propositions for PPI stakeholders, while also deepening the BUILD partners' understanding of the project's objectives.

The insights gained from this activity were utilised throughout the project, ensuring tailored communication for public buyers, suppliers, and multipliers (stakeholders who play a pivotal role in supporting and facilitating innovation, representing both supply and demand perspectives).

2.1.3 Involvement of the stakeholders

The complete strategy for stakeholder mapping and involvement was detailed in D3.2 – Stakeholders Mapping and Scouting. PEDAL was responsible for identifying and mapping contacts of public procurers, suppliers, multipliers, and PPI-related projects, with additional support from partners in compliance with GDPR.

Following this activity, the contacts collected were engaged through a survey, led by CIVITTA and described in detail in D3.3 – Engagement and onboarding. The survey aimed to assess the interest and commitment of stakeholders in participating in BUILD’s training activities, helping to tailor these activities to the actual needs of the audience. CIVITTA drafted, collected, and analysed the survey results to align the training sessions with the interests and requirements of the PPI community.

The survey revealed different levels of engagement across the WP4 training sessions:

- **Training Session 1:** Recorded the highest participation, indicating strong initial interest.
- **Training Session 2:** Showed a slight decline in participation, reflecting sustained but somewhat reduced engagement.
- **Training Session 3:** Had the lowest participation, suggesting a decrease in interest or shifting stakeholder priorities.

These insights were used to plan subsequent activities iteratively. Feedback collected for Sessions 2 and 3 highlighted the need to adapt session content to better align with the evolving priorities of stakeholders. The reduced participation was also likely due to the high level of commitment required to attend all three sessions, as evidenced by the increased number of stakeholders who expressed interest in future sessions despite lower participation rates. During the first session, there was a reflection on how to enhance the relevance of subsequent sessions and to inform stakeholders about upcoming activities. The training activities of WP4 were developed taking into considerations these insights, and the strategy is described in D 4.1 - Report on Training Activities of Public Procurers, D4.2 - Report on Staff Exchanges to Support Mutual Learning and D4.3 - Report on PPI Simulations, Consolidated Training Approach and Updated Training materials.

Additionally, targeted communication strategies, including snowball outreach and continuous dissemination via social media, were essential in refining outreach methods and demonstrating the value of BUILD activities. Engagement campaigns showcased the tangible benefits of participation, and the snowball method (post-sharing through consortium partners, related projects and their networks) attracted additional participants for future training sessions. The BUILD consortium continued using social media to expand the trainee base beyond the initial network.

2.2 Evaluation criteria

The following table shows a quantitative overview of the dissemination and communication, Key Performance Indicators that the project reached:

Tools and channels	Metric method	Target value	Results
Website	Number of visits Number of countries	At least 3.000 visits At least 25 countries reached	>5840 visits on BUILD website and 7435 on the IPTF website 103 countries reached with BUILD website
Flyer/Poster/ Roll-up	Number of promotional	flyers, 100 flyers distributed	-2 flyers, >100 printed (10 at Barcelona City EXPO, 80 in training

	materials created Number of flyers distributed	roll-ups 2 posters	sessions, 70 at final event) -1 roll-up printed (SIPE Conference. For the rest of the in-person activities, partners preferred to print posters due to ecological reasons, as previously discussed with the PO) -1 poster on the BUILD main features. Other information about the project was released through the infographics
Infographics	Number of infographics	10 promotional banners 10 Quiz and Educational cards 1 factsheet “innovation procurement job profiles” 1 factsheet “BUILD PPI model” in 10 EU languages 6 infographics to visualize the main projects’ outcomes 1 Booklet on BUILD Policy recommendations for Private and Public Buyers	-11 banners (BUILD project overview, 5 for training sessions, 2 for training session webinar, 2 for joint webinars, 1 for staff exchanges, 1 for Final Event) -15 quiz cards -1 factsheet on PPI job profiles -1 factsheet on BUILD PPI model in 13 languages -6 infographics on project outcomes -1 Booklet on Policy Recommendations
Multimedia materials	Number of videos produced	At least 1 promotional video 3 video teasers 1 educational video	-1 promotional video -3 video teasers (one about training sessions, one about staff exchanges and one about the Final Event, in collaboration with PROCEDIN) -3 educational videos (PPI introduction, challenges, incentives)
Events and Conferences	Number of speeches at events and conferences Number of publications Number of organised events	At least 10 speeches at events and conferences (live and online) 1 publication 1 Final event to present the BUILD model and outcomes to the European Commission and other relevant stakeholders	>10 speeches (Procurement of Innovation in 2023, Big Buyers Symposium, Barcelona EXPO, Legal Framework workshop, CircularPSP, 2 IPTF webinars, Innovation Conference Belgium Presidency, Energy Management International Conference, InnoFacilitator CoP, Final Event) -1 publication -1 Final Event (in collaboration with IPTF)

Dissemination webinars and presentations	Number of webinars Number of participants Number of meeting with stakeholders	4 informative webinars with at least 50 participants At least 6 meetings with stakeholders (potential adopters, multipliers, etc.)	-5 webinars, participants in brackets (IPTF presentation webinar (28), IPTF on Best Practices (32), 1 online training session (47), 2 training sessions in Estonia (32) and Finland (46)) ->6 meetings with stakeholders (4 training sessions, Final Event, ProCure kick-off meeting, 5 network meetings for procurement specialists in the region, Valonia)
Workshops	Number of workshops Number of PPI talks/seminars Number of capacity building webinars for BUILD procurers	At least 18 co-creation workshops 8 "PPI talks/seminar 5 capacity building webinars for BUILD procurers	-22 co-creation workshops (3 Buddy pairing sessions, 4 market consultations, Final Event workshop, 14 IPTF co-creation meetings) -(1)Policy making session during Final Event, (2)Capacity Building in Action at Final Event,(3) PPI enhancement at Research and Innovation Week, (4)Circular PPI enhancement with CircularPSP, (5)Presentation with the Advisory Board members of Procure project , (6) Projects under the European Innovation Ecosystems workshop, Programme in support of the New European Innovation Agenda workshop, (7) PROTECT project discussion, (8) INEA discussion -6 capacity-building webinars (1 online international training session, 2 hybrid training sessions in Estonia and Finland, 2 webinars on best practices together with IPTF, 1 webinar directly on capacity building)
Social media	Number of members and engagement	At least 250 members on LinkedIn; At least 20 of discussion topics launched on Twitter;	-Total followers across all social media: 929 (303 on LinkedIn, 308 on Facebook; 212 on Twitter; 106 followers on Instagram) >20 topic discussion on Twitter
Email campaign, Newsletter, Press release	Number of email campaigns Number of newsletters Number of press releases	40 email campaigns through partners' channels 4 Newsletters At least 4 press releases	>1500 (1)Engagement survey, IPTF webinars (2), BUILD PPI webinar, Final Event (5 campaigns) PEDAL was the communication manager, the other 5 partners sent at least 2 emails each per each campaign. Turku sent the email campaign for the BUILD workshops and SIPE Conference to

			<p>a total of 1500 people. The rest of the email campaign for the SIPE conference was managed by F6S (PROCEDIN) as the communication manager of the event.</p> <p>Given that there are 6 partners in the IPTF, who sent at least two emails each)</p> <p>-4 newsletter releases (Project first year progression, Second year activities information, Final Event, Project Conclusion and Education Material)</p> <p>-4 press releases (Project Launch, SIPE Conference, Policy Booklet, Project End and Educational Library)</p>
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Table 1 - KPIs overview

2.3 Timeline

This section shows the implementation timeline for BUILD dissemination and communication activities.

Online and electronic dissemination tools	Indicative timeline											
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Social media			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	x
Website			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Press release		x										
Newsletters												
Promotional video			x									
Video teasers												
Flyers	Ad hoc											
Poster/roll-up	Ad hoc											
Events/meetings	Ad hoc											

Online and electronic dissemination tools	Indicative timeline											
	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Social media	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Website	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Press release									x		x	x
Newsletters				x			x				x	x
Promotional video												
Video teasers							x	x	x			
Flyers	Ad hoc											
Poster/roll-up	Ad hoc											
Events/meetings	Ad hoc											

Table 2 - Timeline

3 BUILD identity and promotional materials

3.1 Brand identity development

The BUILD brand identity was a crucial aspect of the communication strategy, which is why it was developed at the very early stages of the project. This identity was consistently used across the various materials produced throughout the project.

The brand identity was essential for launching the communication and dissemination activities, as it helped distinguish the project in the minds of the target audience. It comprised noticeable elements such as the trademark colour, logo, name, and symbol. The first logo proposals were created in early October, and a Google form was circulated for project partners to vote on their preferred option. PEDAL, along with all the partners, made significant efforts to select the ideal brand identity for BUILD.

Following the selection, a manual and communication templates were developed, and the consortium was briefed on their proper use to maintain brand consistency when communicating and disseminating the project's results and activities.

In the following section, the BUILD Brand Identity is presented

- **Final Logo and its variations (vertical, horizontal and colour variations)**

- **The BUILD Colours**

Figure 1 - BUILD logo and features

The BUILD logo was consistently displayed prominently on all communication materials produced within the project framework, including presentations, deliverables, and other materials. Similarly, the EU funding was duly acknowledged, with the EU emblem correctly featured in all communications.

Figure 2 - European Union funding icon

3.2 Templates

As the leader of Communication and Dissemination, PEDAL produced a series of support materials and templates to assist partners in both formal and informal communications. These resources were designed to streamline processes such as reporting (e.g., deliverables template), presenting at meetings and events (e.g., PowerPoint template), participating in events (e.g., folders and letterhead paper), and mass mailing or announcements (e.g., email signature).

The templates created included:

- Word template for deliverables
- PowerPoint template
- Letterhead paper
- Promotional banners made ad hoc

Figure 3 - Power point template

Figure 4 - Word template

Figure 5 - Letterhead paper

3.3 Icons and graphic items

A series of graphic items and icons was developed to characterise the website and all the communication materials (articles, presentations, educational materials etc.). They are displayed in the following section:

Figure 6 - Icons of the BUILD project

3.4 Leaflets, posters and roll-up

The materials developed within BUILD, including leaflets, posters and roll-up are presented below:

Figure 7 - BUILD poster and factsheet

Figure 8 - BUILD leaflet

Figure 9 - BUILD roll-up

3.5 Promotional video and teasers

The promotional videos produced within BUILD are available at the home page of the BUILD project, at the following links:

- BUILD promotional video: http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/BUILD_promo_video_03.mp4
- BUILD video teasers:
 - Training sessions: http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/020_BUILD_video_teasers_01_v04.mp4
 - Staff exchanges: http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/020_BUILD_video_teasers_02_v02.mp4
 - SIPE(Scaling-Up Innovation Procurement) Conference/ Final Event: <http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/SIPE-conference.mp4>

4 Digital tools

In today's world, more people choose to stay informed through digital communication channels. To effectively convey its messages, BUILD focused on establishing a strong online presence across multiple digital platforms to reach a diverse range of stakeholders. Specifically, BUILD created and managed the following, which are detailed in the subsequent sections:

- a website
- various social media channels
- newsletters
- digital press releases

4.1 Website

The first version of the BUILD website was launched at the end of December 2022 (M3) at www.build-procurement.eu. Throughout the project's duration, it was regularly updated with relevant resources, deliverables, articles, synergies, videos, internal and external events, reports, project results, and news from the PPI field.

The BUILD website served as the primary digital dissemination platform, showcasing the project's progress to a broad audience. It was designed to be accessible to the general public, with a user-friendly structure and content aimed at keeping stakeholders engaged.

The website included key information about the BUILD project's concept, approach, team members, and essential insights on public procurement of innovation. All project outcomes, such as public reports, dissemination materials, and newsletters, were available for free download. It also provided information on related initiatives and databases, useful links, the project's privacy policy, and a contact form. While PEDAL, as the leader of WP5 on Dissemination and Communication, was primarily responsible for managing the website and its content, all partners contributed to content development by sharing news and initiatives.

Measures were taken to ensure the protection of personal data. The website was maintained throughout the project and will remain accessible for two years after its conclusion.

Key features of the BUILD website included:

- **Responsiveness:** the platform was optimised for various devices, including mobile, tablet, and desktop versions
- **Social media sharing:** the website enabled users to share information across social media networks such as LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube
- **Mailing list subscription:** a submission form allowed users to subscribe to the newsletter, requiring their name, email, and organization.

The website has the following structure (sitemap) and interfaces:

Figure 10 - BUILD sitemap

Figure 11 - Example of a page of the BUILD website (About)

The BUILD website utilised Google Analytics as its web analytics service to track traffic and gather valuable statistics, helping to optimise both the website and the communication and dissemination strategy. Key statistics monitored included:

- number of visitors
- country of origin

Website links were featured in all promotional materials and communications developed under the project framework, including presentations, infographics, factsheets, brochures, posters, roll-ups, newsletters, social media posts, email campaigns, and events. This helped increase the reach to various audiences and directed them towards the BUILD website.

4.2 Social media

The primary objective of social media was to raise awareness and engage with the target audience. The social media channels used included LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook as the main platforms, with Instagram utilised occasionally to share project outputs. The content shared across these platforms included publications, events, project results, website articles, and synergy activities.

- **LinkedIn:** Tenderio and PEDAL LinkedIn pages were used from Month 2 to enhance the visibility of BUILD at a professional level.
Links:
[Tenderio LinkedIn](#)
[PEDAL LinkedIn](#)
- **Twitter:** <https://twitter.com/tenderiodotcom>
- **Facebook:** <https://www.facebook.com/tenderio>
- **Instagram:** https://www.instagram.com/build_procurement.eu/ – Primarily used to share information, project overview and actionable tools.

The project's social media pages were updated weekly with posts about the latest updates, activities, materials, and relevant news and articles related to the project or common themes associated with the Innovation Procurement Task Force (IPTF). On average, two posts per week were published across all social media channels.

When relevant, the following PPI-related accounts were tagged such as: CORDIS, Horizon Europe, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA), European Innovation Council, European Research Executive Agency.

In addition, related projects and initiatives from the IPTF were also tagged, such as:

- PROCEDIN
- Health InnoFacilitator
- Urban Agenda Partnership for Responsible Procurement
- Procure4Health
- Prepare
- CircularPSP
- InnoBuyer

All consortium partners also used their existing social media platforms to amplify BUILD's activities.

4.2.1 Social media campaigns

Social media campaigns were designed to promote the various initiatives and training topics overseen by the BUILD project. Specifically, the strategy behind the campaigns considered the development of social media posts aimed at sharing the project articles, increasing the traffic to this one, as well as creating a direct engagement on the BUILD social media profiles, through interactive posts inviting the audience to interact.

The social media campaigns covered the following topics:

- Launch of the BUILD project: scope, characteristics and consortium
- Promotion of initiatives, events and training sessions offered by the PPI community, the European Commission
- Introduction to PPI
- Presentation of the Innovation Procurement Task Force and synergies building
- Promotion of BUILD workshops, webinars, events, training sessions, staff exchanges
- Promotion of the project's deliverables and results
- Overview of PPI benefits and best practices
- Promotion of Call for proposals and funding opportunities for innovative companies
- Analysis of challenges and solutions in PPI
- Insights from the BUILD experience: training sessions and staff exchanges
- Policy recommendations
- Real cases and successful examples in PPI

4.3 Newsletters

The BUILD consortium produced four newsletters throughout the project to raise awareness and share the latest news, upcoming activities, and results. These newsletters were distributed to website subscribers and stakeholders who had subscribed during events or other occasions where they consented to receive updates. Partners also shared the newsletters with their personal and professional contacts. The distribution of newsletters became more frequent in the second half of the project to provide actionable information about BUILD's progress, training resources, activities, and events relevant to the audience.

The newsletters are available on the project website and include the following information:

1. Welcome to the project and introduction:

<https://mailchi.mp/a978d3849527/buildprocurementproject>

2. Capacity-building activities: <https://mailchi.mp/a0c83f61f5c0/buildprocurementproject-17984651>

3. Improving PPI adoption and policies: <https://mailchi.mp/a0c83f61f5c0/buildprocurementproject-17984651>

4. Educational Library: <https://mailchi.mp/0b4ea81ccd7e/buildprocurementproject-17984667>

4.4 Press releases

PEDAL prepared four press releases during the project, highlighting important news, milestones, and resources produced. These press releases were shared on social media, the project website, and, when relevant, with media outlets in the partners' respective countries to ensure broader coverage.

The press releases covered the following topics and are available at the following links:

1. **BUILD project launch:** http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/PressRelease_BUILD_1.pdf

2. **BUILD Final Event:** http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Press_release_BUILD_2.pdf

3. **Release of Policy Recommendations Booklet:** http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/BUILD_press_release_3.pdf

4. **Release of the educational library:** http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/BUILD_press_release_4.pdf

5 Dissemination activities

Dissemination was crucial for engaging relevant stakeholders, developing exploitation strategies, and ensuring that project results would be usable by the identified stakeholders at the project's conclusion. Consequently, all consortium partners actively participated in dissemination activities, guided and monitored by PEDAL as part of WP5. This included the development of dissemination materials.

5.1.1 Infographics and banners

The following infographics and banners were produced:

Banners (available in Annex I)

- Training sessions
- Staff exchanges
- Joint webinars
- Final Event
- BUILD training session webinar

Infographics

Figure 12 - Staff exchanges infographic

TRAINING PUBLIC PROCURERS & case studies collection

The BUILD project has conducted targeted training sessions for public procurers across Europe, focusing on best practices and innovative procurement methods. These training programs shared practical examples and fostered knowledge exchange to boost innovation procurement capacity.

KEY DATA

- 316 Participants attended training events across five countries (Ireland, Latvia, Netherlands, Slovakia, and the UK)
- 46 Case Studies (link from the Education Library) from cities like Tartu, Rotterdam, and Tallinn, showcasing diverse procurement approaches.
- Focused on methods such as Competitive Dialogue, Pre-Commercial Procurement, and Innovation Partnerships.

COLLECTIVE LEARNINGS:

- Innovation Procurement arises from necessity: Innovation is driven by the need for new solutions to complex challenges like climate change, biodiversity loss, and rising costs. When conventional methods no longer suffice, innovative procurement becomes essential.
- Lack of Practical Knowledge and importance of peer learning: concrete examples from peers help public procurers navigate when innovation is needed and how to structure the process effectively. Substantive case-based training based on real-world examples of innovative procurement methods.
- Challenge of Innovation Procurement: managing the budget, timeline, and resources for innovative processes is complex. Recognising innovation potential early, structuring procurement accordingly and sharing best practices is key.

CASE STUDY USING COMPETITIVE DIALOGUE Rotterdam

Zero-emission deliveries of goods and services using award criteria focused on emission-free transport. The project fosters innovation in sustainable mobility, overcoming challenges in contract management and ensuring compliance by tracking the suppliers' delivery methods.

Explore more about BUILD's training sessions and gain insights from innovative procurement practices.

http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/BUILD_D4_1_Infopack_Training_Activities_PPayers_MLb_VOC.pdf

Download all the case studies to learn by practice:

<https://www.build-procurement.eu/educational-library/>

Re-watch the webinar on practical Case Studies of Innovation Procurement here:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CY750Zpml8A&list=PL8B3-2008a>

EDUCATION LIBRARY for Innovation Procurement

The BUILD Education library offers a central collection of actionable knowledge for public buyers and stakeholders interested in adopting innovative solutions within the public sector. Drawing from the BUILD project's extensive experience, it provides practical resources, training, and expert insights to enhance innovation procurement.

KEY FEATURES

- **Quick Cards:** Learn PPI principles with fun and interactive quizzes.
- **Educational packages for Public Buyers:** a complete journey to master the adoption of PPI, including an introduction to the topic, training material simulating a complete procurement process, as well as the lessons learned through our procurers team's experience.
- **Job profiles:** explore the different careers available in the world of Innovation Procurement.
- **Webinars:** Re-watch our educational training sessions on YouTube.
- **Policy Recommendations:** enhance innovation adoption in public procurement with actionable policy insights. (paper work)

INNOVATION PROCUREMENT SYNERGIES

Innovation Procurement Task Force (IPTF): Learn about joint initiatives on innovation procurement.

Related Projects: Discover synergies with other EU-related initiatives and their key resources.

- Knowledge pills
- Incentives for Innovation Procurement
- Challenges of Procuring Innovation
- Procedures for Purchasing Innovation

FURTHER READING:

- BUILD Insight Report
- Market Consultations Report

Access the full range of resources in the BUILD Education Library and enhance your innovation procurement capabilities!

<https://www.build-procurement.eu/educational-library/>

BUILD INSIGHT REPORT: best practices in Innovation Procurement

The BUILD project Insights Report highlights innovation procurement strategies from Rotterdam, Tartu, and Tallinn. These cities share the best practices to drive innovation in public procurement for a sustainable future in close relation with innovative enterprises.

WHAT IS INNOVATION PROCUREMENT

It refers to any procurement method by public authorities to buy innovative products or services that yet do not exist or are new to the market to meet their specific needs.

INCENTIVES FOR INNOVATION PROCUREMENT

They can include different actions, such as:

- Measurable target for innovation procurement
- Active plans to increase the amount of innovation procurements
- Practice guidelines for public procurers
- National competence centres
- Strategic goals involving innovation procurement as a tool to reach them

KEY CROSS-CUTTING THEMES OF APPLICATION:

- Low carbon solutions
- Digitalisation of services and processes
- Smart utilisation of Data

NATIONAL COMPETENCE CENTRES:

They aim to stimulate innovation procurement and assist public procurers/practitioners on identifying innovative ideas and bringing them to the market through procurement.

- Dutch Public Procurement Expertise Centre (HARO)
- KUHO Competence Centre for Sustainable and Innovative Public Procurement in Finland
- Estonian Innovation Procurement Competence Centre

PROCEDURES USED TO PURCHASE INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS

- **Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP):** Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) lets public buyers purchase R&D from multiple suppliers, narrowing down options after each phase to find the best solution. In some cases, R&D can be bought without formal procurement.
- **Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI):** Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) allows public buyers to purchase innovative products already on the market but not yet widely available. Buyers can use standard procurement methods (e.g., open or negotiated procedures).
- **Innovation Partnership:** combines both components: buying the R&D and the subsequent innovation (I). It allows public buyers to establish a partnership to develop and subsequently purchase a new, innovative solution. It is a specific public procurement procedure.

PRACTICAL EXAMPLE: how Tartu city fosters innovation

Cost-free infrastructure maintenance, innovative machinery with real-time tracking, and environmental criteria in tenders.

Discover more about innovation procurement through the full BUILD Insight Report.

http://www.build-procurement.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/D2-1-BUILD_Insight-Report.pdf

Figure 13 - Infographics on training sessions, BUILD Insight Report and Educational Library

BUILDING SYNERGIES IN INNOVATION PROCUREMENT: the success of the Innovation Procurement Task Force and the SIPE Conference

The Innovation Procurement Task Force (IPTF) was established to unite European initiatives in driving innovation procurement. The final event of the BUILD project, the SIPE (Scaling-Up Innovation Procurement in Europe) Conference, marked the culmination of efforts to boost the implementation of innovation procurement across Europe.

WHAT IS THE IPTF:

- **Established in January 2024** with founding partners: BUILD, PROCEDIN, and Health InnoFacilitator.
- **Additional partners:** InnoBuyer project, Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative Public Procurement, Procure4Health, P REPARE Project, and many others to join.
- **Mission:** to create a central hub for stakeholders in innovation procurement, fostering collaboration, mutual support and capacity building.

IPTF COMMON GOALS

- **Knowledge sharing:** create a platform for sharing best practices in innovation procurement.
- **Capacity building:** support procurement professionals in developing skills and tools to implement innovative procurement strategies, promoting each others initiatives.
- **Cross-sector collaboration:** encourage partnerships between public and private sectors to overcome challenges in innovation procurement and aggregate resources when possible.

THE SIPE CONFERENCE

June 18, 2024, in Brussels.

- **Policy perspectives:** engaging EU stakeholders in discussions about policy changes needed to make innovation procurement mainstream.
- **Capacity building:** showcased resources from BUILD, PROCEDIN, and Health InnoFacilitator to support the development of innovation procurement skills.
- **Learning lab:** A collaborative session where attendees developed actionable strategies for scaling up innovation procurement.

Explore the full SIPE Conference Insight Report for a detailed overview of discussions, outcomes, and future steps:
<https://iptf.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/IPTF-Conference-Insights-Report.pdf>

Review the Conference key sessions:
<https://iptf.eu/lorem-ipsam-dolor-sit-ametconsectetur-adipiscing-10/>

Join the IPTF:
Similar initiatives are welcome to join the IPTF to further expand innovation procurement across Europe. Contact us: <https://iptf.eu/contact-us/>

EXCHANGING KNOWLEDGE: engaging with the Innovation Procurement community

It's been a long journey sharing our initiatives, training, and resources with the innovation procurement community. The energy and participation from everyone working to bring innovations to our cities has been amazing! All the content we've shared is still available on our website and social media—so dive in and stay connected.

OUR RESULTS

Online community
529 Followers across LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram.
1000+ Social Media Posts published

Articles Published:
70+ Articles published, covering BUILD initiatives and related topics in innovation procurement.

Events and training community
Participation to 12+ events to promote innovation procurement and learn from each other
400+ participants across all our capacity building and engagement activities

MAIN COMMUNICATION CHANNELS:

- **Website:** Regular updates, news, and project deliverables published. Everything you need is here.
- **Newsletters:** 4 newsletters collecting the main project's updates and results. You can check them in our Newsletter section!

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS:

- **Educational library**
Webinars, videos, reports, best-cases examples, it's all there for your innovation revolution!
- **Synergies:** more than 12 connections with initiatives related to PPI

Come back to our BUILD website and social media whenever you need a boost in your innovative procurement practice!

www.build-procurement.eu

Figure 14 - Infographics on synergies and communication goals

5.2 Conferences, events and activities

5.2.1 Internal events

The attendance to the internal events and their overview is summarized in the table below.

Date of Event (day/month/year)	WP/Task (in which event is included)	Event Title	Location (City, Country)	Partners Involved	Type of Event	Audience (number by type of stakeholder)					Total Audience	Promotional Materials (which and how many were distributed)	Collaborations (Nr. of contacts made)	Main Outcomes (Specify the impact for the Project)
						Public buyers	Government and policy	SMEs	Research institutes	Others				
05.12.2022	T2.1	Buddy pairing session	Online	Rotterdam, Tartu, Turku, Valonia	Workshop	x					x			
08.12.2022	T2.1	Buddy pairing session	Online	Rotterdam, Tartu, Turku, Valonia	Workshop	x					x			
15.12.2022	T2.1	Buddy pairing session	Online	Rotterdam, Tartu, Turku, Valonia	Workshop	x					x			
03.03.2023	task 2.2	Innovatiivisten hankintojen työpaja	Turku, Finland	Valonia	Workshop	9					9	12		Barriers and possible solutions related to IP were mapped
09.03.2023	task 2.2	Innovatiivisten hankintojen työpaja	Turku, Finland	Valonia	Workshop	8					8	Unknown due social media posts, public invitations. Straight marketing to 39 municipalities or public organizations	8 public procurement municipalities or organizations	Barriers and possible solutions related to IP were mapped
14.03.2023	task 2.2	Innovatiivisten hankintojen työpaja	Turku, Finland	Valonia	Workshop			15			15	Unknown due social media posts and public invitations. Straight marketing to 6 organizations that promised to share the invite to their wide SME network.	6 organizations when marketing, 15 participants and their organizations	Barriers and possible solutions related to IP were mapped
21.03.2023	task 2.2	Innovatsioonihangete töötuba	Estonia	Turku, Civitta	workshop	5	1	1	1	2	10	invitation was sent to 49 people	15 people participated + 3 moderators	Barriers and possible solutions related to IP were mapped
05.04.2023	task 2.2	Innovatsioonihangete töötuba	Estonia	Turku, Civitta	workshop			2		3	5	invitation was sent to 25 people	7 people participated + 2 moderators	Barriers and possible solutions related to IP were mapped
28.04.23	WP5	Innovation Procurement Task Force	Online	All	Webinar/presentation	x					x	3 emails sent to survey subscribers, 3 posts on SM		Presentation of BUILD, capacity-building
06.23	WP5	Innovation Procurement Task Force	Online	All	Webinar/presentation	x					x	3 emails sent to survey subscribers, 3 posts on SM		Presentation of BUILD, capacity-building

Date of Event (day/month/year)	WP/Task (in which event is included)	Event Title	Location (City, Country)	Partners Involved	Type of Event	Audience (number by type of stakeholder)					Total Audience	Promotional Materials (which and how many were distributed)	Collaborations (Nr. of contacts made)	Main Outcomes (Specify the impact for the Project)
						Public buyers	Government and policy	SMEs	Research institutes	Others				
03.04.24	WP6	Public Buyers Training - Estonia	In presence	Tartu, CIVITTA	Training/presentation	x					15	Leaflets, poster, factsheet, banner, social-media		BUILD training activities and dissemination
04.04.24	WP7	Public Buyers Training - Estonia	Online	Tartu, CIVITTA	Webinar	x					32	Leaflets, poster, factsheet, banner, social-media		BUILD training activities and dissemination
12.04.24	WP4	Public Buyers Training - The Netherlands	In presence	Rotterdam	Training/presentation	x					45	Leaflets, poster, factsheet, banner, social-media		BUILD training activities and dissemination
08-09.04.24	WP4	Public Buyers Training - Slovakia	In presence	PEDAL	Training/presentation	x				x	119	Leaflets, poster, factsheet, social media		BUILD training activities and dissemination
24-25.04.24	WP4	Staff exchange Finland	In presence	Turku, Valonia, Tartu, Rotterdam	Training/presentation	x					15	Banner, social media		Knowledge exchange, capacity-building, dissemination
14-15.05.24	WP4	Staff exchange Estonia	In presence	Turku, Valonia, Tartu, Rotterdam	Training/presentation	x					8	Leaflets, poster, factsheet, social-media		Knowledge exchange, capacity-building, dissemination
29-30.05.24	WP4	Staff exchange The Netherlands	In presence	Turku, Valonia, Tartu, Rotterdam	Training/presentation	x					8	Banner, social media		Knowledge exchange, capacity-building, dissemination
18.06.24	WP5	Final Event - Brussels	In presence	PEDAI, CIVITTA, IPTF partners	Conference/ Training/presentation	x	x	x	x	x	56	Leaflets, poster, factsheet, banner, roll-up, social media, articles	Inspire project coordinator	Knowledge exchange, capacity-building, dissemination
05.09.24	WP5	Presentation on Build project	in presence	Rotterdam	presentation / capacity building	x					50	Poster, 1		Presentation of BUILD, capacity-building
06.03.24	WP4	Webinar on innovative procurement methods	Online	All	Webinar/presentation	x				x		Banner		Presentation of BUILD, capacity-building
27.03.24	WP4	Public Buyers Training - Finland	In presence	Turku, Valonia	Training/presentation	x					14	Leaflets, poster, factsheet, banner, social-media		BUILD training activities and dissemination
28.03.24	WP5	Public Buyers Training - Finland	Online	Turku, Valonia	Webinar	x					46	Leaflets, poster, factsheet, banner, social-media		BUILD training activities and dissemination

Table 3 - BUILD events, report from event tracker

5.2.2 External events

The attendance to the external events is summarized in the table below.

Date of Event	Event Title	Location (City, Country)	Partners Involved	Type of Event (Eg; workshop; conference; fair, exhibition area; etc.)	Type of Participation (eg: only attended; oral presentation; paper submitted; organiser; exhibitor; etc.)	EXTERNAL EVENTS - Audience (number by type of stakeholder)				Total Audience	Promotional Materials (which and how many were distributed)	Main Outcomes (Specify the impact for the Project)
						Public buyers	Government and policy	Start-ups	Other			
21/03/2023	Procurement of Innovation in 2023 – Challenges & Opportunities	Online	PEDAL	Online conference	Oral presentation of BUILD project	X				60+	BUILD short presentation in PDF	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
11/2022	Big Buyers Symposium	Online	PEDAL	Online conference	Oral presentation of BUILD project	X					-	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
11/2023	Barcelona SmartCity Expo World Congress	In presence	PEDAL	Fair	Exhibitor for BUILD project	X					1 poster, 20 flyers	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
06.12.23	Innovation Ecosystems for Circularity' workshop organised	Online	PEDAL	Workshop	Oral presentation of BUILD project	X				25	-	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
07.12.23	Circular PSP Follower webinar	Online	PEDAL	Online conference	Oral presentation of BUILD project	X				20	Short PPT presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
19/03/2024	Research and Innovation week 2024	In Presence	PEDAL	Conference	Oral presentation of BUILD project and discussion on IP enhancement	X				100	-	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
01/04/2024	Energy Management International Conference - Slovakia	In Presence	PEDAL	Conference	PPT short presentation of build, trainer	X				100+	1 BUILD poster and 50 flyers	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
March 2024	InnoFacilitator CoP	Online	PEDAL	meeting	Presentation of BUILD	X			x	22	Short BUILD	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
May 2024	InnoFacilitator CoP	Online	PEDAL	meeting	Sharing information about the IPTF	X			x	18	BUILD logo	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
September 2024	InnoFacilitator CoP	Online	PEDAL	meeting	Sharing about BUILD library	X			x	20	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
23/08/2024	Climate training for upper management in municipalities	In Presence	Valonia	Training	Organiser	X				26	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
19/04/2024	Network meeting for procurement specialists in the region	Online	Valonia	Network meeting	Organiser	X				20	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
16/12/2022	Network meeting for procurement specialists in the region	Online	Valonia	Network meeting	Organiser	X				15	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
26/01/2024	Network meeting for procurement specialists in the region	Online	Valonia	Network meeting	Organiser	X				16	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers

Date of Event	Event Title	Location (City, Country)	Partners Involved	Type of Event (Eg: workshop; conference; fair, exhibition area; etc.)	Type of Participation (eg: only attended; oral presentation; paper submitted; organiser; exhibitor; etc.)	EXTERNAL EVENTS - Audience (number by type of stakeholder)				Total Audience	Promotional Materials (which and how many were distributed)	Main Outcomes (Specify the impact for the Project)
						Public buyers	Government and policy	Start-ups	Other			
15 november 2023	Impactful innovation	In pressence Murchia	CE	Conference	Attended	x	x			100	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
15.05.2024	Innovation workshop	In presence	Tartu, Estonia	Workshop	oral presentation	x	x			20	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
January 2023	Procure project	Online	PEDAL	Meeting	Oral presentation						BUILD logo, short presentation	PEDAL as member of the Advisory board of ProCure, increased visibility for BUILD, nre synergy
January 2023	Protect project presentation	Online	PEDAL	Meeting	Oral presentation						BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers, new synergy
January 2023	Projects under the European Innovation Ecosystems Works Programme workshop /INEA discussion	online	PEDAL	Talk	Oral presentation						BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers, new synergy, discussion on PPI
08/12/2023	Network meeting for procurement specialists in the region	Online	Valonia	Network meeting	Organiser	X				15	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
09/06/2023	Network meeting for procurement specialists in the region	Online	Valonia	Network meeting	Organiser	X				18	BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers
January 2023	Projects under the European Innovation Ecosystems Works Programme workshop	Online	PEDAL	Workshop	Speaker	x					BUILD logo, short presentation	Promotion of the project and its activities, increase of SM followers

Table 4 - BUILD external events,report from event tracker

5.2.3 Final Event

The Final Event took place in Brussels on the 18th of June. The change of location was communicated in time with the PO, who agreed with this choice as it allowed for organizing the event together with the other members of the Innovation Procurement Task Force (IPTF) and provided a more central venue. This also allowed innovation procurement experts, government authorities, and policymakers to join the event more easily.

The event preparation started in the spring 2024 and was performed together with the sister project PROCEDIN and the InnoFacilitator project, who shared professional and financial resources for the successful outcome of the conference. The final event was named the “SIPE (Scaling Up Innovation Procurement in Europe) conference” and aimed to create an interactive event to foster discussions on how to enhance PPI adoption, create synergies, and present the results from the IPTF projects supporting PPI.

The group responsible for the organisation of the event had regular meetings throughout April and May 2024, working on the event outline, agenda, speaker research (gathered through the project consortium’s professional networks), and subsequently the logistics and promotion. PEDAL took care of coordinating the organisation, F6S (from PROCEDIN) managed the communication and creation of the IPTF website, and University of Twente (from PROCEDIN) designed the concept note and content outline of the event. Specifically, PEDAL was the main contact point for the payments for the catering services, venue, overview of the status of speakers invitations, support partners in getting all the necessary information to take action and track the progress of the organisation.

6 The event was structured into three main sections:

1. Policy Perspectives on Scaling Up:

This segment featured a series of brief presentations centered on insights from the IPTF partners. Policy experts then provided commentary, followed by an open discussion. This session focused on sharing and debating policy-related insights from the IPTF projects to deepen the collective understanding of barriers and pathways to scaling up innovation procurement.

2. Capacity Building in Action:

The second session showcased selected outputs from the PROCEDIN, BUILD, and InnoFacilitator projects, illustrating how these resources can be applied to foster innovation procurement capacity building. The BUILD project presented its most useful tools and insights, including the empathy map and resources derived from the training activities. Interactive discussions using persona cards were used to profile needs and challenges, helping potential users identify suitable resources tailored to their specific needs.

3. Innovation Procurement Learning Lab:

This session adopted a "World Café" approach, inviting all attendees to contribute to developing strategies for accelerating and scaling up innovation procurement. Attendees had the opportunity to collaborate in small groups, and at the end, each table presented its findings to the larger group, encouraging collective learning and exchange of ideas.

The event attracted a total audience of 56 participants, including public buyers, EC representatives, policymakers, and SMEs. The communication content was developed by F6S, while the BUILD project adapted the messaging for its social media channels to better target its specific audience. BUILD also promoted the conference through newsletters and several articles on its website and was

responsible for sharing social media posts about the IPTF on its channels, through a dedicated social media campaign.

To maximise the accessibility and availability of the conference, the first and second sessions were completely recorded and are available at the IPTF website to be rewatched.¹

The IPTF, led by F6S produced an Insights Report, describing the main lessons learned from the event. PEDAL developed several articles to present in more depth the conference report. All the articles are available in the dedicated news section of the BUILD project.²

6.1 Production of articles

The production of the articles aimed at:

- Presenting the BUILD project, its strategy and goals
- Promote BUILD activities, resources and events
- Inform the audience about PPI, its characteristics, tools and benefits
- Reciprocally support related PPI projects and initiatives
- Inform the audience about relevant event, both internal and external

The collection of the articles produced within BUILD is summarized in the following table:

Number	Title
1	BUILD project to boost demand for innovative goods and services in Europe
2	Workshop: Projects under the European Innovation Ecosystems Work Programme in support of the New European Innovation Agenda
3	Online webinar – European Innovation Ecosystems
4	Open call for public authorities to develop innovative services
5	Interesting facts on Public procurement of innovation
6	Innovation procurers and their engagement discussed at Value Proposition Workshop
7	Online workshops for buyers and suppliers to enhance their interest in innovation procurement
8	Innovation Procurement Task Force
9	EC's flash report on "Leading the new wave of deep tech innovation" is out
10	Good practice of innovation procurement
11	Procurement of innovation 2023: challenges and opportunities conference
12	Info session: Building Innovation procurement Capability (IPTF)
13	D3.1 Value proposition and Engagement Strategy
14	What is circular procurement and why it is time to scale it up?
15	8 challenges and solutions in Public Procurement of Innovation

¹ <https://iptf.eu/lorem-ipsum-dolor-sit-ametconsectatur-adilespicit-10/>

² <https://www.build-procurement.eu/news/>

16	Understanding the benefits of Innovation Procurement through real-life cases
17	Insights from public procurers' exchange of best practice (IPTF)
18	Empowering innovation procurement: Key insights into best practices and resources from public procurers (IPTF)
19	How to Accelerate Innovation Procurement in Europe
20	Exploring the innovation procurement – the impact on society, environment and economy
21	How to empower sustainable cities via innovation procurement
22	The European Toolkit to lead innovation and tackle future challenges
23	EUR 120 Million for Innovative Projects: call for proposals now open
24	Join the 2023 European Urban Resilience Forum in Cascais, Portugal
25	Smart City Expo World Congress 2023: shaping the Future of Urban Innovation
26	Copenhagen Innovation Summit 2023: join the event
27	18th International conference on smart cities and sustainable solutions (ICSCSS)
28	Procurement Strategies & Innovation (PSI) 2024
29	Leading the way to a sustainable future: Rotterdam's UrbanFuture conference week (UF24)
30	Discover the Future of Procurement at the Procurement Summit 2024
31	
32	Unlock Innovation with Health Innofacilitator's Coaching Services
33	10th European Conference on Sustainable Cities & Towns: Aalborg2024
34	Challengers meet Solvers thanks to InnoBuyer's market consultations
35	11th Procura+ Conference invitation
36	Bridging the gap: Innovation Procurement for real-world urban challenges
37	International conference on Innovation Procurement by the Programme for Innovation Procurement (PIP)
38	Elevate your innovation: the 11th Successful R&I Europe Conference

39	Accelerating Circular Economy Solutions with AI: CircularPSP's Tender Unveiled
40	BUILDing Innovation Procurement Capacity: A Year in Review
41	BUILD Project's 2024 Roadmap: A Year Full of Knowledge Discovery and Cooperation
42	PROCEDIN's WHITE PAPER: Key Elements of Procurement of Innovation, Part 1
43	Navigating the Landscape of Innovation Procurement: Lessons learnt by cities
44	Starting Innovation Procurement Journey: Insights and Advice from Leaders
45	Free training on innovative procurement methods by BUILD
46	Overcoming Barriers in Innovation Procurement: the Lack of Capacity
47	Tackling Challenges in Procurement Innovation: Addressing Risk Aversion
48	Procurement Leaders Envisioning the Future of Innovation Procurement
49	Unveiling Innovative Procurement Strategies: Lessons from the BUILD Webinar
50	In-Person Training Sessions on Innovative Procurement Methods (PPI)
51	BUILD shares learnings on innovation procurement at the Research and Innovation Week 2024
52	BUILD Project: Empowering Innovation Procurement through Targeted Training for Public Buyers
53	BUILD Training Sessions for Public Procurers: Insights from the Finnish Procurement Landscape
54	Innovation Procurement Capacity Building: Insights from Estonia's Training in Tartu
55	Geemente Rotterdam Hosts Innovative Training on Public Procurement
56	Empowering Sustainability: Slovakia Hosts Training on Innovation Procurement
57	5 Lessons Learned from BUILD's Innovation Procurement Training Sessions
58	Join Us at the SIPE Conference: Scaling-Up Innovation Procurement in Europe
59	
60	Building Partnerships Training Session: Consortium Building in Innovation Procurement
61	Strategies for Successful Innovation Procurement Through Staff Exchanges

62	Driving innovation in smaller municipalities: BUILD staff exchange in Tartu
63	Learning between diversity and shared challenges: The first BUILD staff exchange in Turku
64	Rotterdam, the city of innovation and experimentation – get inspired!
65	Report on staff exchanges to stimulate mutual learning is out
66	Scaling Up Innovation Procurement: Perspectives for Effective Policies
67	Capacity Building in Innovation Procurement: a critical need for public buyers and strategic objectives
68	Fostering Collaboration and Innovation in Public Procurement
69	Real-World Examples of Successful Strategies in Innovation Procurement
70	Key Recommendations for a Successful Implementation of Innovation Procurement
71	BUILD project releases Policy Recommendations to strengthen Innovation Procurement in Europe
72	BUILD white paper: an overview on the power of public procurement as a tool to purchase innovation. Challenges and incentives

6.2 Educational library

The Educational Library developed by the BUILD project is a comprehensive collection of the knowledge generated during training sessions, preparatory activities, and joint efforts with the IPTF and related PPI initiatives. This knowledge was transformed into accessible, user-friendly documents, reports, infographics, and factsheets, available to all PPI stakeholders. The BUILD consortium collaborated through shared documents and preparatory meetings to ensure the accurate development of educational content, while also presenting it in an accessible and well-designed format. Specifically, PEDAL as leader of this task, drafted a preliminary plan, description and main features for each single material, to which the rest of the consortium provided technical inputs and their general feedback to make the resources as useful as possible. PEDAL then worked on the graphic development and upload on the website, making them available for the BUILD audience.

The KPIs to reach for the Educational library are the following:

>25 content for >15 resources and >5 innovative formats. #15 Educational cards/quizzes, #1 factsheet “PPI job profiles”, #3 educational and information packages for public buyers, #1 Lesson plans and training contents for public buyers,#1 factsheet with BUILD PPI model.

To reach them, the following strategy was designed and undertaken:

The 15 sources are the following.

1. Valonia, Turku, Tartu, PEDAL, CIVITTA, Rotterdam knowledge
2. IPTF and synergies (PROCEDIN, InnoBuyer, Health InnoFacilitator, Procure4Health, Prepare, Urban Agenda Partnership for responsible procurement)
3. European Innovation Council

4. [IPP Platform](#)
5. BUILD D4.1, D4.2, D4.2, D3.3
6. BUILD publication
7. Events (SIPE Conference, Procura+, HealthInnoFacilitator webinars, CircularPSP webinars, Innovation week, etc)

The 5 innovative formats specifically for innovation procurement are:

1. Quiz cards/gamification
2. Webinars
3. Open access training library (Sway platform)
4. AI generated videos
5. Infographics

The 25 contents of the educational library are the following, which are available at this link:

<https://www.build-procurement.eu/educational-library/>

- 1 Lesson plan
- 3 Educational packages for Public Buyers (Introduction to PPI, PPI simulations and consolidated training approach, Lessons learned)
- 15 quiz cards
- Collection of 8 best-case practices
- Policy Recommendations booklet to enhance PPI adoption
- 2 Webinars on PPI methods and exchange of best practices
- SIPE conference report and session video
- BUILD factsheet in 13 languages
- Factsheet on job profiles in PPI
- Synergies in PPI (IPTF, related projects and initiatives, PROCEDIN Resources bank, Training workshops by the Health InnoFacilitator project)
- 3 knowledge pills (Incentives, challenges and procedure in PPI)
- Market consultation report
- BUILD Insights Report
- Report on Insights on the training sessions for public buyers
- Mutual learning across cities with BUILD staff exchanges report
- BUILD publication: white paper "An overview of Public Procurement as a purchasing tool for Innovation: challenges and incentives"

What are the common hindering factors that can affect innovative procurement?
 A) Only financial and legal challenges
 B) Political/Administrative, Organizational, Financial/Mission, Knowledge and Skills, Legal (Correct answer)
 C) Only mission and organizational challenges

When can a government organization legally establish that an innovation process qualifies for an innovation partnership?
 An innovation process qualifies for an innovation partnership when a government organization has a specific need for which no existing solution is available in the market. Legally establishing the innovation demonstrates that the required solution does not currently exist and that the development of a new solution is necessary to meet the organization's needs.

How does pre-commercial procurement differ from traditional procurement?
 Answer: Pre-commercial procurement is focused on finding research and development to create innovative solutions that are not yet available on the market, whereas traditional procurement involves purchasing existing products or services.

What characterizes a competitive dialogue procedure in public procurement?
 Answer: A competitive dialogue procedure is characterized by a structured dialogue between the buyer and bidders to refine project requirements before final proposals are submitted. This process is typically used for complex contracts where detailed and tailored solutions are needed.

Why is legal knowledge crucial in public procurement?
 Answer: Legal knowledge is crucial because it ensures that procurement processes are handled with integrity, provides the best results for the best value, and allows for competition among companies by putting contracts out to tender and giving all interested companies an equal opportunity to carry out an assignment.

When is the competitive procedure with negotiation used in procurement?
 Answer: The competitive procedure with negotiation is used when there is a need to clarify or improve bids with bidders after the submission of fully formed sealed tenders. This approach is particularly useful when the buyer cannot fully define the technical needs to meet their needs or specify the legal or financial requirements upfront.

What are the benefits of an innovation partnership in procurement?
 Answer: An innovation partnership allows for co-development between the buyer and the supplier during the procurement process, which is particularly beneficial when the details of the required solution are not yet clear. This approach fosters collaboration and innovation to create a tailored solution that meets the buyer's needs.

What are the common legal obstacles encountered in innovative procurement, and how do they relate to knowledge, experience, and mindset?
 A. Evaluation and feedback help identify strengths and weaknesses, and opportunities and improve processes, leading to more effective and efficient outcomes in future contracts.
 B. Evaluation and feedback should only focus on their relevance and not on improving processes.
 C. Evaluation and feedback should only focus on their relevance and not on improving processes.

How do evaluation and feedback (e.g., from the contracting authority or the end user) improve public procurement processes?
 A. Evaluation and feedback are only necessary for unsuccessful projects.
 B. Evaluation and feedback help identify strengths and weaknesses, and opportunities and improve processes, leading to more effective and efficient outcomes in future contracts.
 C. Evaluation and feedback should only focus on their relevance and not on improving processes.

What are the three key guiding principles of public procurement?
 A. Cost effectiveness, Transparency, Equal Treatment
 B. Transparency, Non-discrimination and Proportionality, Equal Treatment (Correct answer)
 C. Efficiency, Non-discrimination, and Equal Treatment

What characterizes a competitive dialogue procedure in public procurement?
 Political and administrative factors can hinder innovative procurement by introducing bureaucratic, red tape, slow decision-making processes, and a lack of political will or support for new approaches.

How do financial challenges affect innovative procurement?
 Answer: Financial challenges include budget constraints, funding issues, and a risk-averse approach to spending, which can limit the resources available for pursuing innovative solutions.

Why is risk assessment critical in innovation procurement?
 Risk assessment is critical in innovation procurement because it allows you to identify and estimate the potential risks and benefits associated with pursuing a new solution. By understanding these risks, you can find a balance that maximizes the potential benefits while minimizing potential downsides, ensuring a more successful and sustainable procurement process.

What are the common legal obstacles encountered in innovative procurement, and how do they relate to knowledge, experience, and mindset?
 Innovation procurement requires a blend of technical, legal, and managerial expertise. Lack of understanding of procurement regulations, slow decision-making, and a risk-averse approach to spending can hinder innovative procurement. To overcome these challenges, procurement professionals need to gain knowledge, experience, and build a mindset that is open to innovation and willing to take calculated risks. This involves a combination of the regulator framework, rather than relying on a full range of high-ambition.

What is the primary purpose of a preliminary market consultation?
 Answer: The primary purpose of a preliminary market consultation is to publicly early engagement from the market to refine project requirements and shape the procurement strategy, thereby reducing risks associated with receiving feedback too late in the process.

How do evaluation and feedback (e.g., from the contracting authority or the end user) improve public procurement processes?
 Correct answer: B

JOB PROFILES IN INNOVATION PROCUREMENT

Innovation Procurement plays a critical role in enabling public sector organisations to access new, innovative solutions to meet societal needs. By leveraging innovative procurement strategies, governments can support innovative enterprises while improving the efficiency and quality of public services.

Specialized job profiles are essential in ensuring the success of these innovation-driven initiatives.

KEY JOB PROFILE OVERVIEW

Innovation procurement requires a blend of technical, legal, and managerial expertise.

PROCUREMENT JOB LEVELS

Procurement support Procurement Practitioner Procurement Specialist Procurement Executive

Under supervision: Low-risk, low value contracts Supervision: High-risk, high value contracts, Strategic management, Expert Procurement advice

CAREER PATHWAYS

They are closely related to the size of the public organisation. In smaller municipalities, procurement staff often have less specialised roles and handle various tasks, while larger municipalities may have more specialised procurement profiles.

EDUCATION AND SKILLS REQUIREMENTS

Education: Bachelor's or Master's degrees in fields such as Business, Supply Chain Management, Civil Engineering, Urban Planning, Environmental Science, or Public Law. Additional certifications in public procurement, project management, or procurement tools may be beneficial.

Technical Skills: Strong knowledge of procurement processes, contract management, supply chain, and legal frameworks. Proficiency in e-procurement tools, project management software, market analysis, and procurement law.

Soft Skills: Strong communication, negotiation, teamwork abilities, strategic thinking, and leadership.

JOB PROFILES

Procurement specialist - specialist in a specific field (e.g. infrastructure planning)
 Senior Purchasing Advisor
 Development Specialist
 Market and technology analyst
 Stakeholder engagement lead

Funded by the European Union

Figure 15 - Factsheet on PPI job profiles and printable quiz game

6.3 Partners involvement and reporting

All consortium partners contributed to the project's dissemination by:

- mapping local and national actors from the identified target groups to create an initial pool of stakeholders
- regularly participating in the project's reports and internal communications
- promoting the project's progress and results through their own professional websites, blogs, and social media channels
- sharing press releases at the national level
- conducting dissemination activities within their respective countries
- participating in external and internal events, such as conferences, workshops, and relevant scientific and EC-driven events
- identifying relevant news and information for BUILD's social media channels and website, and informing PEDAL
- identifying key exploitable results and developing strategies for their exploitation during and after the project's duration

6.3.1 Internal reporting

Tracking the dissemination, communication, and engagement activities conducted by all partners was crucial for the successful implementation of the project. To ensure effective dissemination of the BUILD project, as well as to facilitate tracking and reporting, an Excel template for dissemination reporting was created and shared with the consortium via G-drive. Partners regularly updated this template. The reporting sheet collected data on social media posts, and both internal and external events that were organised or participated in by the consortium.

7 Cross-collaboration with project partners and related initiatives

The consortium collaborated with other ongoing projects, aiming to establish synergies with research and innovation initiatives, particularly those funded by the EU through Horizon Europe or other funding programmes, with a specific focus on projects fostering PPI. This helped to increase project visibility on websites, newsletters, and conferences, exploiting opportunities for knowledge exchange and enhancing dissemination and communication with the target audience. The following R&D projects were considered relevant to developing the BUILD concept:

Collaboration with related projects and initiatives was crucial for ensuring broader outreach, sharing knowledge, and maximising attendance at project trainings and events. BUILD worked closely with IPTF members, which included:

- PROCEDIN
- Health InnoFacilitator
- InnoBuyer
- Urban Agenda Partnership for Responsible Procurement
- Procure4Health
- PREPARE

These partners supported BUILD's communication by sharing events, training sessions, articles, and policy recommendations with their respective audiences when deemed appropriate.

The biggest collective achievement of the Task Force was the organisation of joint webinars on PPI and the final event – SIPE (Scaling Up Innovation Procurement in Europe) held in Brussels.

PEDAL also promoted relevant initiatives organized by the European Innovation Council.

Conclusions

The dissemination and communication activities carried out throughout the BUILD project were instrumental in ensuring the project's visibility and engagement with its target audience. These activities aligned with the Communication and Dissemination Plan (DCP) and the description and goals stated in the Grant Agreement, allowing the consortium to achieve the project's communication goals and maximise the impact of its outputs.

Throughout the project, all consortium partners played an active role in the dissemination process, engaging stakeholders, and ensuring that key messages and results reached the appropriate audiences. The project utilised a wide range of communication channels, including the website, social media, newsletters, press releases, and participation in external events. These efforts were critical in fostering knowledge sharing and collaboration across the Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI) community.

Iterations and adjustments were made during the project's implementation to enhance the effectiveness of communication and ensure the best delivery of project outcomes. The collaboration with related initiatives, such as the Innovation Procurement Task Force (IPTF) and other EU-funded projects, further strengthened the project's dissemination efforts, broadening its outreach and increasing stakeholder engagement.

The BUILD project successfully developed a range of communication materials, including reports, infographics, videos, and the Educational Library, which provided accessible resources to stakeholders across the PPI landscape. All project outputs were delivered as planned, with communication efforts ensuring their visibility and long-term impact.

Moving forward, the BUILD website will remain active for five years, ensuring continued access to project resources and supporting further engagement with the PPI community. This extended online presence, combined with the lessons learned during the project's communication activities, will help sustain the impact of BUILD's achievements. Also, the resources will be published on the IPTF's website to maximise their visibility and make them available for a wider audience, gathered from all the initiatives part of the Task Force.

Access the BUILD Educational Library

Lesson plan with three educational packages for Public Buyers
(Introduction to PPI, PPI simulations and consolidated training
approach, Lessons learned)

15 quiz cards

Collection of 8 best-case practices

Policy Recommendations booklet to enhance PPI adoption

Webinars on PPI methods and exchange of best practices

SIPE conference report and session video

BUILD factsheet in different languages

Factsheet on job profiles in PPI

Synergies in PPI (IPTF, related projects and initiatives, PROCEDIN

Resources bank, Training workshops by the Health

InnoFacilitator project)

3 knowledge pills (Incentives, challenges and procedure in PPI)

Market consultation report

BUILD Insights Report

Insights on the training sessions for public buyers

Mutual learning across cities with BUILD staff exchanges

[Access it here](#)

Annex I

Promotional banners

Final event

Training session webinar

Joint webinars

BUILD
Public Procurement of Innovation

Funded by the European Union

BUILD Staff exchanges

BUILD Public Procurers gather together to share insights and practices on Innovation Procurement

TURKU **Gemeente Rotterdam** **TARTU**

Funded by the European Union

Leer meer over innovatieve inkoop methodes: gratis training

Datum: Vrijdag 12 april van 9:00 tot 12:00 uur
Locatie: Timmerhuis (halvemaanpassage 1) in Rotterdam, Ruimte 5.023
Sprekers: onder meer Leyla Bozkurt (advocaat aanbestedingsrecht) en Godard Croon (trainer circular inkoop)

Let op: er zijn slechts een beperkt aantal plaatsen beschikbaar, dus meld je zo spoedig mogelijk aan via dit emailadres: nam.koendjharie1@rotterdam.nl

BUILD **Gemeente Rotterdam**

Funded by the European Union

Innovatiivsete hankemeetodite alane koolitus

Aeg: 3. aprill 2024 kell 13.00-16.00
Koht: VSpa, Finland hall, Riia 2, Tartu ja Online via Teams

Registreerimine: Kasutage kirjelduses olevat linki. Tähtaeg: kohapeal on 27. märts, internetis 1. aprill
Maksustus: Tasuta

TARTU **BUILD** **civitta**

Funded by the European Union

Innovatiivisia hankintamenetelmiä koskeva koulutus

Aika: 27. maaliskuuta 2024 klo 9-12
Paikka: Yliopistonkatu 27, 20100 Turku

Ilmoittautuminen: Maaliskuun 22. päivään 2024 mennessä kuvauksessa olevan linkin kautta.
Kustannukset: ilmainen

VALONIA **BUILD** **TURKU**

Funded by the European Union

Školenie o inovatívnych metódach obstarávania

Dátum: 8. a 9. apríla
Miesto konania: Konferencia Energetický manažment 2024 v Grand Hoteli BELLEVUE, Horný Smokovec

Registrácia: vyplňte formulár v popise a pošlite ho na konferencie@sstp.sk.
Náklady: pozrite si podrobnosti o konferencii

TURKU **VALONIA** **PEDAL** **BUILD** **Gemeente Rotterdam** **TARTU** **civitta**

Funded by the European Union

In-person training sessions on Public Procurement of Innovation

Boost your innovative procurement methods with our local experts

Tartu, Estonia 3rd April at 13-16	Horný Smokovec, Slovakia 8th April at Energetický manažment 2024	Turku, Finland 27th March at 9-12	Rotterdam, Netherlands 12th April at 9-12
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TURKU **VALONIA** **PEDAL** **BUILD** **Gemeente Rotterdam** **TARTU** **civitta**

Staff exchanges and training sessions